

Managing Editor's Column

Vol. 29, No. 1

Dear Readers,

I would like to wish you all the best for the new year! It is with great pleasure that I welcome you to our first regular issue in 2023, which contains 4 highly relevant and novel articles on various topics in computer science.

Looking back at the past year, we successfully increased our visibility and improved the J.UCS platform by featuring the most frequently accessed articles each month on Pensoft Publishers Ltd.'s ARPHA Publishing Platform. Thanks to the combined efforts of the Pensoft team and the J.UCS publishing team, we are listed and indexed in more than 40 indexing services worldwide, including DOAJ, Web of Science, and Scopus. The increased visibility and social media presence has also led to a further increase in page views and article downloads, with around 45000 unique views, as well as an increasing number of submitted articles and special issue proposals. We are also very pleased to report that the journal's Impact Factor has continued to improve with a Web of Science Impact Factor of 1.056 and a Scopus Science Score of 2.7. We are proud to look back on a total of 12 issues with 56 articles by 172 authors from 33 countries on new aspects of various topics in computer science; more precisely, the articles were published in two special issues and ten regular issues.

These great achievements were only possible because of the commitment and interest of the community, the valuable support of the Editorial Board, and the support of the members of the J.UCS Consortium. In 2022, we welcomed 12 new Editorial Board members, reaching a total of 189 Editorial Board members. We also gratefully acknowledge the support of 56 guest reviewers during the past year. In particular, I would like to thank Dr. Ulrike Krießmann from the Library of the Graz University of Technology, Prof. Klaus Tochtermann from the ZBW, Prof. Christian Eckhardt from California Polytechnic State University, and Prof. Krzysztof Pietroszek from the American University in Washington DC for their generous support in offering an open content journal without charging the authors for their articles. I would also like to thank the J.UCS team, Johanna Zeisberg for taking care of the publication process, Aleksandar Bobic for his social media support, and Alexander Nussbaumer for his technical support, as well as Pensoft Publishers Ltd. for hosting our journal.

I look forward to continuing to work with our editors, editorial team and technical support to maintain the success of J.UCS. I would be very grateful for suggestions and feedback on how we can make J.UCS even better and evolve in the future. We also greatly appreciate the generous support of the J.UCS community, especially in promoting the journal and citing relevant articles in their research papers.

In this regular issue, I am very pleased to present 4 accepted articles from 16 authors from 6 different countries.

Purvaja Balaji, Helena Merker and Amar Gupta from MIT in the USA introduce in their article an automated, three-step pipeline to solve the challenge of text classification, specifically to automate the labeling of each sentence in an input document consisting of section titles and section text. In a research collaboration between Colombia and Belgium, Oscar I. Caldas, Mauricio Mauledoux, Oscar F. Aviles and Carlos Rodriguez-Guerrero conducted a study to measure objective indicators of engagement while study subjects played an immersive virtual game with DDA to find evidence of dynamic response similar to game performance. Robert Ehrensperger, Clemens Sauerwein und Ruth Breu from University of Innsbruck in Austria present in their article a maturity model for comparing and assessing Digital Business Ecosystems (DBE), which was developed based on the Design Science methodology, the review of 22 scientific publications and the interviews of 28 senior experts. In their joint research between Chile, Japan and Colombia, Matias Salinas, Paul Leger, Hiroaki Fukuda, Nicolas Cardozo, Vannessa Duarte and Ismael Figueroa outline their integrated programming environment Incre-IDLE, specifically designed for first-year students, and an evaluation revealed that it is easier to use for the target group compared to professional IDEs.

Enjoy Reading!

Cordially,

Christian Gütl, Managing Editor-in-Chief
Graz University of Technology, Graz, Austria
Email: c.guetl@tugraz.at